

Ichneumonid parasitoids of the rice yellow borer in West Bengal, India

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The yellow stem borer population has often been low in the multiple rice cropping system on the alluvial soils of West Bengal. One reason for the low insect density may be the many parasitoids that attack yellow borer larvae or pupae. Parasitoids have also been found in sweep-net collections. The ichneumonid parasitoids found at the Chinsurah station, and identified after the type specimens by the Commonwealth

Parasitoid	Host stage	Time of collection	Remarks
<i>Temelucha philippinensis</i> (Ash.)	Larva and Pupa	Feb, Aug, and Dec	Also found in light trap
<i>Temelucha stangli</i> (Ash.)	Pupa	July	
<i>Isotima javensis</i> (Rohw.)	Larva and pupa	Feb, May, and Nov	
<i>Amauromorpha</i> sp.	Pupa	Apr	
<i>Trathala flavoorbitalis</i> (Cam.)	—	Aug to Nov	Only in sweep net
<i>Eriborus</i> sp.	—	Aug to Nov	Only in sweep net
<i>Xanthopimpla</i> spp.	—	Aug to Nov	Only in sweep net
<i>Goryphus mesoxanthus maculipennis</i> (Cam.)	—	Nov	Only in sweep net

institute of Biological Control, Bangalore, and by the key in IBP Handbook 14 are listed below. Further work on the host

range and relative abundance of the parasites is in progress. ■

Effects of spacing on rice hispa incidence

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A field trial was laid out in kharif 1978 to study the effect of spacing on rice insect incidence. Forty-five-day-old seedlings of PR106 were transplanted in 5- × 4-m plots at 3 spacings. Each spacing was replicated three times. Recommended agronomic practices were followed (120 kg N, 30 kg P₂O₅, and 30 kg K₂O/ha). The rice hispa *Dicladispa armigera* was the predominant species attacking the crop. The damaged leaves on selected 10 hills from each plot were counted.

Although the differences in

Incidence of rice hispa in different spacings (mean of 9 observations). Kapurthala, Punjab, India.

Spacing (cm)	Damaged leaves ^a (av no./10 hills)				Mean
	20 DT	40 DT	60 DT	80 DT	
10 × 10	12.0 (3.43)	3.9 (1.96)	10.0 (3.15)	10.9 (3.28)	9.2
20 × 15	17.2 (4.14)	6.8 (2.56)	15.3 (3.80)	17.2 (4.13)	14.1
30 × 30	34.8 (5.79)	11.8 (0.42)	15.2 (3.90)	23.0 (4.70)	21.2
C.D. (P = 0.05)	(n.s.)	(1.39)	(n.s.)	(n.s.)	

^aFigures in parentheses arc/√n transformations. DT = days after transplanting. n.s. = nonsignificant.

hispa-damaged leaves in 3 spacings were significant only at 40 days after transplanting, the widely spaced plants were damaged more severely. There were 9.2, 14.1, and 21.2 hispa-damaged leaves per 10 hills in the 10- × 10-cm,

20- × 15-cm, and 30- × 30-cm spacing, respectively. The rice hispa prefers widely spaced plants probably because it lays eggs on leaf tips, which are better exposed in widely spaced plants. ■

Some new weed hosts of rice hispa recorded in India

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The rice hispa *Dicladispa armigera*, previously a minor rice pest in the Punjab, recently has become serious.

In 1978 kharif the weed flora at the Kapurthala Rice Research Station was intensively surveyed to determine if they serve as food plants for rice hispa. Adult hispa beetles were found on some common Gramineae weeds such as

Echinochloa crus-galli, *E. colona*, *Paspalum distichum*, and *Cynodon dactylon*. *E. crus-galli* and *E. colona* were generally found in and around rice fields, but *P. distichum* and *C. dactylon* were found mostly on bunds around the fields. The leaves of the attacked plants showed characteristic hispa feeding injury. There were, on the average, 29, 12, 12, and 11 adult beetles/10 plants on *E. crus-galli*, *E. colona*, *P. distichum*, and *C. dactylon*, respectively.

E. crus-galli, *P. distichum*, and *C. dactylon* are new additions to the list of weeds known to host the rice hispa in India. ■

Rice green leafhopper susceptibility to vamidothion in central Taiwan

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Rice green leafhoppers (GLH) collected at 5 locations within a 30-km² area in central Taiwan were tested by topical application for susceptibility to vamidothion, an organophosphorus insecticide for GLH control in Taiwan. Populations from two locations (A and E,

see table) were resistant to the chemical when compared with the most susceptible population (C), and using a resistance ratio of 5 as the demarcation.

No apparent relationship between susceptibility to this compound and the cholinesterase activity of the populations could be found, although the most resistant population (E) showed the lowest cholinesterase activity, and the least sensitivity to vamidothion. When populations E and B were compared, a resistance ratio of about 6 was found associated with an I_{50} ratio of about 5. The results indicate that reduced cholinesterase activity and a change of

Vamidothion susceptibility, cholinesterase activity, and sensitivity of rice green leafhoppers in central Taiwan.

Population	Location	LD ₅₀ (µg/g)	Resistance ratio	Cholinesterase	
				Activity (µmol/min)	I ₅₀ M
A	Shu-wang	10.57	8.7:1	0.069	4.40×10^{-4}
B	Wu-fu	5.53	4.5:1	0.093	2.70×10^{-4}
C	Hsia-tien	1.22	1.0:1	0.054	3.60×10^{-4}
D	Nay-hsin	4.07	3.3:1	0.057	5.00×10^{-4}
E	Lu-tsun	32.10	26.3:1	0.050	1.44×10^{-3}

the target site sensitivity could play a considerable role in vamidothion resistance in GLH. Electrophoretic

studies revealed qualitative differences in esterase zymograms among the populations. ■

Effect of selected insecticides on striped stem borer eggs

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Eggs of the striped stem borer *Chilo suppressalis* in the blackhead stage were treated with candidate insecticides at 0.04% concentration. Before treatment, each egg mass was examined under the microscope to determine the initial number of eggs per mass. Three egg masses were dipped in insecticide solutions for 5 minutes then transferred to a petri dish with moistened filter paper

Effect of selected insecticides on eggs of the striped stem borer. IRRRI 1979.

Insecticide	Formulation	Eggs (initial no.)	Unhatched eggs (no.)	Ovicidal ^a activity (%)
Methyl parathion	50 EC	661	622	92.9
Carbofuran	12 F	596	593	99.4
Methomyl	90 WP	619	600	96.5
Triazophos	40 EC	656	588	89.1
Control		586	163	26.4

^a Av of 4 replications, each containing 3 egg masses.

and kept in an insectary for 48 hours. The eggs were counted again to determine the number that were unhatched. Larvae that emerged and died alter hatching

were considered hatched. Each treatment was replicated four times. The table shows the results. ■

Soil and crop management

Preference for ammonium sulfate as first topdressing in lev method of rice cultivation

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Farmers in Karchhana Tahsil, Allahabad district, commonly direct-seed rice with little field preparation after the onset of the monsoon. To control weeds, they then plow the crop with a deshia plow and plank it under flooded conditions

when plants are about 1 month old or 15–21 cm tall. The practice is locally called *lev*. Progressive farmers in the area claim that ammonium sulfate is superior to urea as the first topdressing in that rice-cultivation method. An experiment in farmers' fields was conducted to investigate the claim.

Sixteen farmers' fields, selected during 1978 kharif, were prepared with two cross plows. No basal fertilizers were applied. The variety Saket 4 was broadcast seeded at 100 kg seed/ha in the first week of July. Five weeks after

sowing the plots were plowed twice with a deshia plow and planked under flooded conditions. In the first eight plots, ammonium sulfate was topdressed immediately after plowing; in the other eight plots, urea was topdressed a week after plowing. Both fertilizer treatments were at 40 kg N/ha. The second topdressing was applied uniformly in all plots about 10 weeks after sowing with 30 kg N/ha as urea.

Visual observations 2 weeks after the first topdressing showed that weed re-establishment, weed density, and weed